

THE EDIBLE CITY GAME 2.1

Not released

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1 Background

This document is defining the framework and parameters of the Edible City Game version 2.1, a serious game for scenario simulation of nature-based solutions for food production, called hereafter Edible City Solutions (ECS).

Specifically, the Edible City Game is one of the tools developed within the EdiCitNet project and a key element of the co-creation philosophy of the project. It aspires to be a valuable contribution to designing the transition to more edible cities. In this sense, the Edible City Game will address several operational objectives of the project:

OB2: Provide Follower Cities (FC) with open access EdiCitNet comprehensive knowledge base and methodology for successfully adapting and implementing ECS – WP2.

The Edible City Game can be used for scenario analysis by urban planners and policy makers as well as by City Teams. The game offers a reference scenario, which is the situation of the city at the beginning of the session. During the session, the players are defining a possible future scenario. It can be through a bottom-up process by several players representing stakeholders' interests or in a top-down process where one player is leading all actions.

OB3: Integrate ECS into urban planning of 8 FC, customised to their specific needs and context - WP4

The Edible City Game is a suitable tool for a participatory planning approach. The players can see the direct consequences of the changes in the city, visually (in a 3D world environment) and through the indicators' outcomes. At the same time, the urban planners can evaluate the decisions and preferences of the stakeholders while they are playing and making decisions in a virtual environment based on their city.

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1.1 Why a serious game?

Nowadays, serious games are one of the most innovative tools to engage citizens on participatory decision-making, often described as being a magic bullet in current governance debates (Ampatzidou et al., 2018). Serious games for urban planning provide a complex problem-solving space: (1) they provide an abstracted model of a problem, fostering an accelerated understanding of a complex issue; (2) they provide a structure for interaction, a model for learning while having a finite set of rules; and (3) they allow individuals to see direct consequences of their actions as of others' actions and decisions (Constantinescu et al., 2017). Besides that, including serious game into urban planning also facilitates social learning, empowering citizens on urban planning, and participatory processes become more enjoyable (Ampatzidou et al., 2018). Therefore, the main aim of serious games is to provide a learning scenario. In this sense, serious game can provoke different learnings or experiences: **(1) a sense of purpose through the establishment of shared goals; (2) fostering reflection by showcasing users' behaviour and (3) facilitate the exploration of complex systems and their interactions** (Gordon & Baldwin-Philippi, 2014).

1.2 A review of concepts for serious game design

The design of a serious game is an important part of the process to ensure citizen's engagement. The main goal of the design process is to find the balance between playful and learning. In other words, to ensure that the game fulfils the learning expectations for which has been designed whereas players enjoy the experience (Ampatzidou et al., 2018; Constantinescu et al., 2017).

A first step of the design is the classification of the elements of the game. In this sense, a game can be divided in the following elements (Poplin, 2014):

1. Environment: it is the static elements of the game, mainly the user interface such as menus, initial screens, etc.
2. Objects: the dynamic elements of the game, i.e. the elements which can be modified by the player.
3. Goals: the achievements that the player needs to get to win the game.
4. Rules: the defined interactions among all elements of the game
5. Players: the elements that lead the interactions with the objects to win the game (they can be actual people or virtual machines).

Another concept of the game design are the game's loops. A loop is the process of the interactions between player's mental model and the game's rules (Cook, 2012). When players start a game, they attempt to figure it out how they can interact with the game following their own assumptions (mental model), this is confronted with the actual possibilities of the game (defined by the rules) and the feedback modifies the players' mental model. Through the loops, the knowledge of players about the game increase as well as their engagement. However, when a loop is broken (i.e. the players is not capable of overcoming the loop because it is too difficult or not progressive or not intuitive enough), the game is no longer attractive for the player. Moreover, some loops might need skills acquired in previous loops. Hence, the game must become more complicated step by step through the loops, creating skill chains.

Figure 1. Game's loops

This approach is in line with another iterative approach that focuses on three elements of the games: the MDA framework (Hunicke et al., 2004). The MDA framework splits the game in three elements: Mechanics, Dynamics and Aesthetics; and provides an iterative process where the game is designed, evaluated by users and improved to a new version following users feedback (Constantinescu et al., 2017). Within the framework, the mechanics are, essentially, the environment, the objects and the rules, as defined above. The dynamics are the interaction between the game's mechanics and the players (that can be conceived as loops but also as the motivation to achieve the goals and, in serious games, the learning opportunities provided by the game). Finally, the game's aesthetics is how players perceive the game. Therefore, the aesthetics cannot be defined by the designer because they depend on the players' perceptions. Here resides the importance of the iterative design. While designer is looking at the mechanics, players look at the aesthetics, which find each other in the dynamics. Once the designer gets the players' feedback, the mechanics can be modified to fulfil the aesthetics expectations.

Figure 2. The designer and players perspective based on MDA framework (Hunicke et al., 2004)

However, any game design, especially when they are co-designed or iterative, must have a rigorous quality control. Indeed, rigorous empirical evidences that proves the serious games capacity to generate learning is still lacking (Ampatzidou & Gugerell, 2019). Therefore, it is important to design a robust quality system in parallel with the design. Specifically, the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) provides a quality model for game design that has been adapted to the serious games design (Cevallos & Santorum, 2019). This adaptation provides a criteria list to define a serious game step by step and a list of good practices to implement in the design process.

One of the steps of the CMMI is, indeed, the mechanisms to get the users' feedback. This feedback can be divided in pre-game, in-game and post-game (I. Mayer, 2012) and can use several methods depending on the stage (Ampatzidou & Gugerell, 2019):

- Pre-game: Survey
- In-game: direct observation, audio or video recordings
- Post-game: Survey, focus group.

Getting users' feedback on the game is useful for several reasons. Firstly, it is crucial to improve the game and, thus, to foster the players' engagement. Furthermore, feedback should also provide empirical knowledge on how the serious game is generating social learning and empowering citizens. Hence, filling the knowledge gap detected by previous literature.

2 The Edible City Game design

With this precedent, we design our serious game combining these two frameworks from literature: the iterative MDA framework (Constantinescu et al., 2017; Hunicke et al., 2004) and the extension for serious games of CMMI-Dev 1.3 (Cevallos & Santorum, 2019). While the CMMI guides the design through a list of specific steps, the MDA, complemented it by the perspective of loops, which indicates when these steps should consider an iterative process (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Framework for design

2.1 Identification and analysis of the situation

“The situation” in our case is a participation process to plan ECS scenarios in the city. The members (city team²) are already engaged in the project, thus the aim of the SG is not fostering

² The city teams are groups conformed in each city compound by stakeholders involved in edible city solutions. They involve citizens, local NGOs, SMEs and policy makers.

participation but doing it more insightful by providing a complex problem-solving space where members will be able to discuss about different scenarios and how ECSs can improve the city.

2.2 Purpose of serious game and learning goals

As mentioned above, the purpose is to provide a complex problem-solving space where city teams debate about the best scenario for their edible city.

Following the 8 Learning Event model (Leclercq & Poumay, 2005), which is a theoretical model to design learning environments, there are two learning experiences that are expected from the game:

- **Experimentation:** The player can manipulate the environment and, when necessary, modify it. Experimentation processes mostly by exhausting and combining the possibilities the player regards as meaningful to test a personal hypothesis. The initiative is player's, the role of session facilitator is to provide an “experimentable” environment.
- **Debate:** Learning takes place during social interactions between pairs provided there are conflicts of views (called socio-cognitive conflicts), challenging discussions forcing the opponents to justify their position or to modify it. The initiative is player's, the role of facilitator consists in “animating” the discussion, this expression covering a wide range of functions, from the less invasive (observation during the debate and debriefing after the debate) to the most invasive ones (such as selecting inputs, i.e. moderating in a forum), passing by a series of intermediate roles (reframing, reorienting, regulating the debate, participating to it).

Within this learning experiences, the specific learning goals (LG) are:

1. To showcase the main urban challenges and how they can be measured (Raymond et al., 2017).
2. To understand how different ECSs address these urban challenges.
3. To empathize with other stakeholders in the city and their conflicting interests.
4. To reach consensus about strategies to implement ECSs with the City Team

2.3 Users characterization and learning environment

The users are the members of City Team in each city. They are stakeholders involved in an ECS or interested in them. The group is probably diverse regarding age, skills and background. This is a challenge because the game must be playful for everyone, finding the balance between being too simple and too complex.

The learning environment is a two-hours session in an indoor space. The game is online, but the conversation during and after the game should be face-to-face to foster the debate and the empathy among users.

To deal with the abovementioned challenges, different game modalities, explained in section 2.8, have been designed to adapt different players with different skills. The game modality can be decided some hours before the session to adjust the game mechanics to the players characteristics.

2.4 Learning methods

As mentioned above, the session is taking place in the online game and face-to-face in parallel. The online game will foster the experimentation learning event while the face-to-face sessions will promote the debate among participants.

Before starting the game, players receive a briefing about the main aspects of the game: goals, interface demo, main rules, strategies... This way the facilitator can easier focus the attention of players on the session purposes. For instance, she can remark face to face negotiations as a strategy or highlight a specific zone in the city where the players should focus their actions.

The game's storyline will be used to showcase the urban challenges (LG 1) of the city by showing the indicators (based on the urban challenges) for their city during the game session. The mechanics of the game are designed to provide an experimentation scenario where users can implement and test their hypothesis about ECSs and how those address the urban challenges (LG 2). For instance, a player could construct an edible rooftop garden and she will see how the city indicators change regarding this new ECs in the city. Is the city more resilient to the climate change? Has social justice increase? Has more green jobs been provided? And, the most important, does it match with my previous beliefs? In most of modalities, a stakeholder's role is assigned to each player to promote the empathy among the stakeholders, while in others the consensus within teams is reached (LG3). At the same time, the players will need to help each other to achieve progress within the game, the possible synergies and trade-offs will be negotiated face-to-face during the game session (LG3 and LG4). At the end of the game a debate will be promoted by revisiting the actions made by each player in the session (LG3 and LG4).

In the most complex modalities, the game will be divided in three levels to add complexity in a progressive way to ensure an enjoyable experience while overcoming the game's loops. After each completed level, the players will have more goals to achieve and more actions will be available to them. Each level will be provided by a storyline for each character in according to the goals and actions for that character in that level.

2.5 Game typology

The game is an urban planning simulator based on digital 3D real-based scenario of the city. It is played in a multi-player session, i.e. the players play at the same time in a shared session where they can interact within the mechanics of the game and among them face-to-face or by sending messages, doing requests, buying and selling land, among others. However, it can be also played in single-player sessions. In addition, some modalities force the players to interact face-to-face.

After checking the different possibilities, the game is designed on Tygron's platform (www.tygron.com/en), since it is the platform that best fulfils the requirements.

2.6 Serious content

The serious content refers to those elements of the game that are intended to fulfil the learning goals. In the Edible City Game, the indicators are the main element of the serious content. The indicators show the current conditions of the city based on different data such as function values, overlays, global values (all of them defined in the following sections). Besides, a target is defined for each indicator. The target is the goal to achieve by the players regarding that indicator.

The indicators are intended to address all aspects of the urban challenges (UC), which has been adapted from Raymond et al. (2017) and are:

1. Climate resilience (CR)
2. Water management (WM)
3. Green space management (GS)
4. Air quality (AQ)
5. Urban regeneration (UR)

6. Participatory planning and governance (PP)
7. Social justice and social cohesion (SJ)
8. Public health and wellbeing (PH)
9. Potential for economic opportunities and green jobs (PE)
10. Food sovereignty (FS)

From these UC, XXXX indicators have been defined to measure these urban challenges, some of them are related to the benefits of ECS while others refer to general urban aspects. Each indicator regards directly to one UC, but it also can provide indirect measurements of other UC (Table 1).

Table 1. Relationships among indicators and urban challenges

	CR	WM	GS	AQ	UR	PP	SJ	PH	PE	FS
Heat island effect	■							■		
Water management	■	■								
Green accessibility			■		■					
Air quality				■				■		
Public participation						■		■		
Green justice			■		■		■	■		
Green economy									■	
Food sovereignty	■							■		■
Green social housing					■		■			
Renewable energies	■								■	

Legend: ■ Primary UC □ Secondary UC

The indicators have been based on Eklipse project's recommendations (Raymond et al., 2017) and adapted to the possibilities and requirements of Tygron's platform. Consequently, there are some UC that are not directly measured by any indicator. They are, specifically, Urban Regeneration and Public health and wellbeing. In the case of UR, the indicators regarding ECSs were redundant with Green Space management according to indicators proposed by Raymond et al. (2017) and measurable on the Edible City Game. And in the case of PH, the only applicable indicator to ECSs was the number of people being physically active, which was assumed as involved people in ECSs, from PP, assuming that people is physically active when they are participating in the ECSs. In addition, other factors have been proved to directly influence public health, the most obvious one is air quality, but also a good access to green areas and a cooling city that diminishes the effects of heat waves.

Although the green social housing and renewable energies indicators are clearly related to UC, they are not related to urban agriculture, which is the game's topic. After testing the version 1.0 the players considered that some actions should compete with ECs for the available space. Therefore, these two indicators are assumed to play this role, green social housing is competing for the land whereas solar panels compete for the roofs.

Moreover, the design of the indicators fostered a balance between accuracy and comprehensibility regarding game players. The outcome of all indicators is a score which is displayed on the game (as a percentage). The score is forced to range between 0 and 1 and depends on predefined targets for each indicator. The targets have a default value defined in line with previous studies. However, it can be easily changed to fulfil the requirements of a specific city or to adjust the achievements to get by the users. The indicators' details are explained below.

2.6.1 Heat island effect

Higher temperatures are one of the major threats of climate change and urban areas are generally warmer than surrounding rural areas. This so-called “urban heat island” is usually caused by heat absorption in paved material which enlarge heat accumulation during the day. The heat stress indicator is a predefined indicator on Tygron’s platform. As explained in the platform’s documentation, the heat stress is measured by a barometer of UNESCO-IHE. In the barometer, the heat stress depends on the distribution of heat in relation to the type of land use. Different types of land use are responsible for the warming or cooling effect compared to the ambient temperature. More information can be found on Tygron’s wiki³.

The heat stress indicator reflects the heat stress average of a neighbourhood. The score is calculated by the next equation:

$$Score = \frac{Max\ target\ value - Average\ heat\ stress}{Max\ target\ value - Target} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

Where, *max target value* is a predefined constants which equals to 1.5. By default, the target is set as -2. The indicator’s score is the average score of all playable neighbourhoods.

2.6.2 Water management

Water storage is key in water management since it helps lowering the flooding and provides an alternative source of water. Open water ponds create the most storage. Additionally, innovative measures and upgrades can be applied to create extra water storage.

The water management indicator is calculated by a function’s value that represents the water storage capacity of that building in m³/m². Hence, the indicator’s score is the proportion of the total water storage of the city regarding the target.

$$Score = \frac{\sum ws_i * a_i}{1000 * target * s_c} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Where *ws_i* is the water storage capacity of the building *i* (in m³/m²); *a_i* is the surface occupied by the building *i*; and *s_c* is the surface occupied by all buildings (in m²) of the city *c*, multiplied by the target (in litres) multiplied to 0.001 to convert to cubic meters. The target is defined by default to 100 l., which is the threshold for a cloudburst (100 litres in 24 hours).

2.6.3 Green accessibility

Greening cities contributes to an increase in wellbeing and enhances the attractiveness of open spaces in cities. At the same time, greening strategies are becoming essential ingredients in urban regeneration (Haase et al., 2017). Within this, ECSs can become green areas where people not only stay and use but also engage with (Säumel et al., 2019). This indicator has not been related to public health UC because several studies found that only access to green spaces, without considering others aspects such as socioeconomic factors, are not related with a health improvement (Tamosiunas et al., 2014; Zuniga-Teran et al., 2019).

The European guidelines for the availability of local public open areas (Tarzia, 2003) defines the minimum distance to a green area as 300 metres for any house. However, this target is little

³ [https://support.tygron.com/wiki/Heat_effect_\(Function_Value\)](https://support.tygron.com/wiki/Heat_effect_(Function_Value))

ambitious and most of cities fulfil them. Accordingly, the indicator measures the proportion of houses that are closer than 100 m. to a green area, including parks and ECSs.

$$Score = \frac{\text{houses closer than 300 m. to a green area}}{\frac{Target}{100} * \text{total of houses}} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

By default, the target is set to 100% (all houses must fulfil the condition).

2.6.4 Air quality

Emissions from motor traffic are a very important source of air pollution in cities around the world and NO₂ is one of the preeminent pollutants emitted and the easiest to measure, thus a good advisor of the total motor traffic pollution (H. Mayer, 1999). Besides, air quality and NO₂ emissions are also directly related to public health, especially to respiratory diseases but also heart diseases and lung cancer (Kampa & Castanas, 2008).

At the same time, vegetation has the ability to remove air pollutants through dry deposition, this contribution can achieve to absorb till 40% of NO₂ emitted by cars (Pugh et al., 2012).

Therefore, this indicator measures how much NO₂ is absorbed by vegetation, including ECSs, compared with NO₂ emitted by motor traffic as follows:

$$Score = \frac{Absorbed\ NO_2}{\frac{Target}{100} * Emitted\ NO_2} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The target is the proportion of NO₂ that vegetation should absorb. By default, it is set to 0.4, following the abovementioned study. The emitted NO₂ is calculated by Tygron's platform according to traffic flows, for more information see Tygron's wiki⁴. Only vegetation which is in contact with concentrations higher than 1 µg/m³ are considered to calculate the amount of absorbed NO₂. The capacity of NO₂ sequestration is set 0,05 ug/s/m² for all green areas, including ECS (Eom et al., 2017).

2.6.5 Public participation

Communitarian ECSs foster public participation and share decision-making among all participants, thus empowering the citizens. At the same time, people who participate in ECSs are more physically active since most of the work in ECSs is physical. Therefore, growing your own food is a proved antidote for sloth and obesity (Säumel et al., 2019).

This indicator measures the number of people involved in ECSs in each neighbourhood, estimated from real ECSs of the EdiCitNet database.

$$Score = \frac{People\ involved\ in\ ECSs}{\frac{Target}{100} * Inhabitants} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

The indicator's score is the average score of all neighbourhoods. The target is the percentage of people that should be involved in ECSs in an optimal scenario.

⁴ [https://previewsupport.tygron.com/wiki/Traffic_NO2_\(Overlay\)](https://previewsupport.tygron.com/wiki/Traffic_NO2_(Overlay))

2.6.6 Green justice

In green infrastructure planning, quite attention has been devoted to environmental justice, which includes elements of distribution, procedure and recognition. In this context, distributional justice relates to the unequal distribution of environmental qualities such as public green spaces (Kabisch & Haase, 2014; Rutt & Gulsrud, 2016). In addition, a more fair distribution of green areas, that is, closer green areas where they are more needed because of socioeconomic issues, addresses more effectively the urban regeneration and the public health UCs, since it is in deprived neighbourhoods where they are more crucial (de Vries et al., 2013).

Hence, this indicator measures the public and private green surface per capita in any neighbourhood and considers the minimum value among all neighbourhoods. The private green surface is considered besides public because, otherwise, neighbourhoods with less surface of private gardens (usually poorer) will be penalized by the indicator. Hence, the indicator is calculated as follows:

$$Score = \min \left(\frac{\sum green\ surfaces_i}{inhabitants_i} \right) * Target^{-1} \quad (Eq. 6)$$

Where i is the neighbourhood. By default, the target is set 9 m²/capita, following the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO, 2010).

2.6.7 Green economy

Green infrastructures offer an opportunity for the creation of so-called “Green-Collar jobs”, from low-skill, entry level positions to high-skill, higher-paid jobs (Falxa-Raymond et al., 2013). In the context of ECSs, professional initiatives that are intended to generate some source of income by producing, processing or using food are a proper tool for self-employment as well as for running SMEs with capacity to employ third people (Säumel et al., 2019). The creation of Green-Collar jobs is more able to have a real impact in areas where unemployment is higher. Therefore, the indicator measures the number of jobs created by ECSs in relation with the work force (inhabitants between 16 and 65) of each neighbourhood:

$$Score_i = \frac{Jobs\ created\ in\ ECS_i}{\frac{Target}{100} * work\ force_i} \quad (Eq. 7)$$

Where i is the neighbourhood. The indicator’s score is calculated as the average score of all neighbourhoods. By default it is set to 3%, in line with proportion of people working in primary sector in western countries.

2.6.8 Food sovereignty

Modern cities almost exclusively rely on the import of resources to meet their daily basic needs, causing several environmental impacts but also social and economic. A study made in Cleveland estimated that Cleveland could produce between 4.2% and 17.7% of the overall consumed food in the city regarding different scenarios, considering fresh produce, eggs, poultry and honey (Grewal & Grewal, 2012). In addition, own-grown food has a direct impact on diet changes, inducing people to consume healthier food, with an obvious impact on public health (Leake et al., 2009; Russo et al., 2017).

Within this context, ECSs have an obvious role in cities becoming self-reliant in food since their most direct outcome is the food production. This indicator measures the food production (in kg/year) in the city in relation with the overall food demand. The average food consumed by a person in a year is assumed as 300 kg (FAO, 2009).

$$Score_i = \frac{Food\ production_i}{\frac{Target}{100} * 300 * inhabitants_i} \quad (Eq. 8)$$

Where i is the neighbourhood, and the target is the proportion of food sovereignty to achieve (by default, 17%, following the abovementioned study). The indicator's score is calculated as the average score of all neighbourhoods.

2.6.9 Renewable energies

Energy from fossil fuels like carbon and oil is one of the biggest cause of climate change. The transition to renewable energies seems unavoidable and European Union is doing a great effort on that. In urban environments, the more feasible renewable energy is the solar through solar panels (Redweik et al., 2013). Therefore, this indicator considers the surface occupied by solar panels on roofs compared by the total roof surface of the city.

$$Score = \frac{Solar\ panels\ surface}{\frac{Target}{100} * Roof\ surface}$$

In addition to these 8 indicators, players also have a budget indicator to control their finances.

2.6.10 Green social housing

The availability of housing is an important challenge for cities. Issues like gentrification and touristification are expelling the more vulnerable neighbours from their homes. Urban greening is also provoking gentrification processes (Rutt & Gulsrud, 2016) when it is not accompanied by social housing policies. In this line, this indicator is considering not only the amount of social housing but also if these actions are avoiding this so-called green gentrification:

$$Score = \frac{Floor\ surface\ of\ green\ social\ housing}{\frac{target}{100} * floor\ surface\ of\ housing}$$

Where *Green social housing* is social housing closer than 100 m. to a public green area and social housing is buildings of category *Affordable housing* or that own to any character with this indicator in her assignment. This way the indicator only increases the score when social housing is close to urban green. The target is defined in % of surface. The total scores is the neighbourhoods' average.

2.7 Edible City Game's mechanics

From the MDA framework, only mechanics intervene in the game definition, because dynamics and aesthetics depend on the interaction with players and their perceptions and influent the mechanics of subsequent versions, which are assessed by a survey and direct observations of the game session. Moreover, the mechanics of a game are defined, basically, for their environment, objects and rules (Poplin, 2014). Therefore, the environment, objects and rules of Tygron's platform used by and adapted for the Edible City Game are explained hereafter.

2.7.1 Edible City Game environment

The environment of Tygron's platform starts with some initial screens:

- Collaborators: To showcase institutional information and acknowledgements
- Game explanation: The game is explained to players by using a short text.
- Definition of the session game: Players must accord a name for the session.
- Stakeholder election: Each player chooses the stakeholders that wants to play with.
- Assignment: The goals for level 1 of the chosen stakeholder are detailed to the player.

In the specifics of the Edible City Game, the first screen that players find is the contributors screen with all the contributors' logos.

Figure 4. Contributor's screen (the logos order is randomly changing every 5")

The story is presented in the game explanation screen. The game is about adapting the city through the construction of ECSs to address the urban challenges.

The players are told that they have been chosen to represent their interests in the city plan. Each one must fill their progress bar, which is a weighted average of a combination of the indicators that represent the stakeholder's interests. Indicators weighting are introduced to the players once they have chosen a stakeholder:

Congratulations!

You are one of our local heroes! In the next hours you are destined to save our city from the dangers that are coming.

Our city is facing important challenges: heat waves are devastating each summer, cloudbursts are flooding our streets, citizens are getting ill because the air is polluted, inequality is increasing, affordable fresh food is more difficult to find from time to time and, incredibly, most of citizens remain apathic in front of it. You are our last hope!

Through this contest, you will be able to propose and build solutions to make your city a better place to live. But everything is not so beautiful, at the same time you improve the city following the common interest, you must defend the interests of your sector and your budget.

And remember, you are not alone, some other heroes are sitting next to you. Let's work together to improve the city!

Good luck in this adventure! All of us depend on you!

Figure 5. Introduction screen with the game story

After the introductory screen, the players must agree on a session's name and then they can choose with which role they are going to play. Once the stakeholder is chosen, each player watches her assignment, that is, the indicators weighting in the progress bar.

Figure 6. Player's assignment screen (in this case, a fictional assignment for the Municipality)

For demonstration purposes, all texts are set in English in this document. However, they will be translated according to the official language of each city.

After this initial step, the 3D world is visualised, and the game is ready to start. The players are welcomed with a fly through the 3D world. There are four menus available to the player:

- Left menu: the actions that player can do.
- Top menu: The stakeholder, the time, the displayed scenario, the indicators and the progress bar.
- Top-right menu: a navigator to turn around 3D world, to switch between 2D and 3D views and to look for specific addresses.
- Bottom-right menu: The information menu, it contains the available overlays, a measuring tool and a log panel with the information of all actions made in the session.

Figure 7. Tygron's platform environment

Different icons are visualised over the 3D world when a stakeholder is required to do some action like accepting an offer, approving a construction...

Figure 8. Symbol of an offer received to buy some of your land

Besides the players interface, Tygron's platform also provides the session with a facilitator and a beamer. The facilitator is basically the admin of the session. She can pause the game, accept or reject players, send messages and money to specific roles and other issues related to the session.

The beamer has the mission to showcase different screens, it is handled by the facilitator in a different screen that should be visible to all players, for instance on a projected screen. The beamer can showcase the indicators' progress, the stakeholders' progress or a specific overlay or indicator.

2.7.2 Edible City Game objects

Regarding the objects, the following objects shape the Edible City Game:

Buildings: Buildings are the unit of the 3D environment. A building refers to everything that can be built or grown up in a city (buildings, squares, streets, parks, trees...). Building are defined by a shape in the 3D world (shape, colour, number of floors, slanting roof...) and a list of numeric attributes such as heat effect, manning value, percentage of green, water storage...). Infinite

numeric attributes can be created for each building. The attributes are used to calculate indicators. A building is divided in sections (floors) that allow to configure more specific visual attributes. Each building is owned by a stakeholder. The buildings are hierarchically organised in functions and categories (explained below), see Figure 9.

Figure 9. Hierarchical organization of buildings on Tygron's platform

Functions: The buildings are grouped in functions. A function is the purpose of a type of building (house with garden, offices, deciduous tree, pedestrian street...). Like the buildings, the functions have attributes too, the function's attributes are set by default in all buildings that pertain to this function.

Categories: Functions are grouped in categories (a more general function for the building). However, a function can be divided among different categories, for instance: a shop with houses is divided between Market housing and Shops and restaurants. Categories are mainly used for indicators' calculus. In a function divided among categories, each category can be weighted for more accurate calculus, i.e. the function "shops with houses" can weight 0.3 in "shops and restaurants" and 0.7 in "market housing". For instance, if an indicator uses the number of houses in a neighbourhood and a player construct a "shops with houses" building, it only will use 0.7 in the indicator calculus instead of 1. Categories are predefined and cannot be modified.

Figure 10. Example of some functions within the category market housing

Although the buildings in the 3D world are context dependent, the functions are not. Therefore, ECSs are created in the form of new functions in the Edible City Game as follows. The creation of ECS followed several criteria:

1. Aim: Communitarian (run by volunteers) or professional (business-based).
2. Technology: Soil-based or hydroponics
3. Structure: On the ground, rooftop or vertical garden
4. Plants: Vegetables (horticulture) or fruit trees (orchard).

From the feasible combinations of previous elements, followings ECS were created for the game with the corresponding attributes:

Table 2. ECS functions

ECS	Description	Construction cost (€/m²)	Heat effect (°C)	Water storage (m³/m²)	NO₂ sequestration (ug)	People involved per m²	Jobs created per m²	Food production (kg/year/m²)	Is public green?
Communitarian garden	Allotment run by volunteers. Soil-based garden is cheaper.	20	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	1	yes
Communitarian hydroponic garden	Hydroponic garden run by volunteers. Hydroponic technology maximizes yield	200	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	2	yes
Communitarian hydroponic rooftop	Hydroponic garden run by volunteers on a roof. Hydroponic technology maximizes yield	200	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	2	yes
Communitarian orchard	A fruit trees plantation run by volunteers. Trees maximize environmental benefits.	20	-8	0	0,05	0,1	0	0,5	yes
Communitarian rooftop garden	Communitarian garden on a roof. Ideal to green the city roofs.	20	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	1	yes
Edible school garden	Students can grow vegetables in the school garden.	20	-6	0,01	0,05	0	0,01	5	yes
School rooftop garden	Students can grow vegetables on school roof and garden area is not lost.	20	-6	0,01	0,05	0	0,01	5	yes
Professional garden	Allotment run by a SME or a cooperative. It creates more jobs than hydroponic gardens.	40	-6	0,01	0,05	0	0,01	10	no
Professional hydroponic garden	Hydroponic garden run by a SME or a cooperative. It	200	-6	0,01	0,05	0	0,01	5	no

	maximizes the yield.								
Professional hydroponic rooftop	Hydroponic garden on a roof run by a SME or a cooperative. It maximizes the yield.	200	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	0,5	no
Professional orchard	A fruit trees plantation run by a SME or a cooperative. Trees maximize environmental benefits.	40	-8	0	0,05	0,1	0	0,5	no
Professional rooftop garden	Allotment run by a SME or a cooperative. Soil-based garden is cheaper.	40	-6	0,01	0,05	0,1	0	0,5	no

* Attributes in italics are specifically created for this game, the others were predefined by Tygron platform.

However, rooftop gardens are not standalone functions, they are joined with different types of functions corresponding to buildings. They are not constructed as new functions but as upgrades of already existing buildings in the scenario. For instance, an apartment could be upgrade to an apartment with a communitarian rooftop garden. Likewise, already existing trees in the city can be upgrade to fruit trees, corresponding to communitarian orchard.

Similarly, city streets can be converted to communitarian gardens which stroke the traffic on that street and computes like a communitarian garden.

Edible school garden and school rooftop garden are equivalent to communitarian garden and rooftop garden, respectively, but it can only be used to upgrade schools.

Moreover, the attribute regarding absorbed NO₂ will also be included in all green surfaces of the model such as city parks and gardens.

Terrain: Terrain comprises the composition of the surface and their elevation. It is classified in land covers, such as open land, water rivers, dunes, etc.

Neighbourhoods: The neighbourhoods delimit the area of the city districts. They can have numeric attributes such as inhabitants, average income, cultural diversity... They are usually used to split the indicators outcomes. They also define the playable area, each neighbourhood can be set as playable or not.

Zoning plan: Actions of stakeholders can be tested against a zoning plan. Each action which requires a permit will need to be approved in accordance with the zoning plan. The zoning plan consists of individual zones, each with specific requirements that an action must conform to. There are two types of zones:

- **Zone without categories:** A stakeholder is assigned to each zone, any new construction must require the approval of this stakeholder.
- **Zones with categories:** Some categories are not allowed. Hence, the action cannot be approved unless the zoning plan is modified.

In this version of the Edible City Game, only zones without categories are used, and the municipality is the stakeholder who must permit the constructions in all zones. Similarly, upgrades in buildings that the player do not own, require the owner's permission.

Overlays: An overlay is a layer drawn over the 3D world to illustrate different properties. Different overlays can be made available to stakeholders to guide their actions. Some examples of layers are heat stress effect, liveability, neighbourhoods, traffic noise... Their function is merely informative.

Figure 11. Heat stress overlay

The following overlays are available to the players:

- Distance to green areas: An overlay displaying the distance of each point to the closest green area.
- Neighbourhoods: An overlay displaying the neighbourhoods boundaries and names.
- Food production: An overlay showing where the ECSs are located (the already existing ones but also the ones created during the session) and how much food is produced, based on EdiCitNet simple models.
- Property: An overlay that identifies the ownership of each building, to make easier to players to know who's the building is.
- Traffic intensity: An overlay displaying the traffic intensity, based on mobility data of the city.
- Heat effect stress: An overlay with the differences in the atmospheric temperature, based on UNESCO-IHE.
- Constructed: An overlay to highlight constructed land. With this overlay, players can search for unconstructed land available to build.

Messaging: Each player is provided with a messaging service to receive and send messages to and from other stakeholders.

Budget: The budget is the amount of money that each stakeholder starts with. It can be modified by the facilitator at each moment of the session.

Global values: Values that are general for the game, they are defined by the designer. For instance, it could be inhabitants, land price...

There are some objects that depend on the city where the game is to be played. The data to construct them relies on the available data of the city. Those objects are the initial buildings, the terrain, the neighbourhoods, the zoning plan and the global values. As more data and more accurate it is, the more realistic the game will be.

2.7.3 Edible City Game rules

Above all rules, Tygron's platform provides two kind of games: timeline and planned. Timeline mode simulates an actual modification of the city, the buildings have a construction time and the players must set up the starting date of the construction. Planned mode simulates an urban planning process, the new buildings are visualized on the 3D world like in timeline mode but they are not really constructed, they are planned buildings. However, the indicators and overlays are calculated as these new buildings really existed. It makes the game less complex and provides an interesting feature: the players can revert their actions, like an undo option.

The Edible City Game is designed to be played in planned mode. However, it can be changed at any time without affecting the rules of the game.

Regarding specific rules, some of them are set by default on Tygron's platform and they cannot be changed, the following ones are the ones affecting the most the mechanics of the Edible City Game:

- To construct or to demolish a building, the player must own it.
- Upgrades change one function by another, internally, the game is demolishing a building and constructing a new one in their place. It is not possible to upgrade a building by changing some attributes. However, it is not necessary to own the building.

Many other rules can be set in each game, these rules are structured in levels, thus each level can have their own rules. Configuring different levels allows the facilitator to change some mechanics in a session by changing the level that users are playing in. For instance, a first level could have some options not available to allow the players to get used with the game. Once the players were familiarized with the game, the facilitator could change the game to the second level, with more options available and, thus, more complexity. A change of level can also be automatically triggered by some event in the session, for instance, some player doing a specific action or after a specific amount of time. The number of levels is configured by the designer. Within each level, four elements can be defined:

1. Stakeholders' actions
2. Playable neighbourhoods
3. Assignments (indicators and their weights)
4. Events

In this first version, three levels will be defined, each one more complex than the previous one regarding number of available actions and complexity of assignment (i.e. more indicators to consider).

The actions are the core of the game, they define what the stakeholders can do to interact with the 3D world and with other stakeholders. There are different groups of actions available on Tygron's platform and used by the Edible City Game:

- **Construct functions:** To construct any building in the 3D world in an empty space of their property. It comes with a financial cost defined by the function's values.
- **Upgrade:** To construct improvements in an existing building, for instance, a green roof. Or to change the function, for instance, from shops to offices. The upgrades must be predefined. Cost and "must own" properties can also be defined.
- **Revert:** In planning mode, the players can undo their constructions and upgrades.
- **Demolish:** To demolish any building of their property. It comes with a cost defined by the function's values and it depends whether the building is vacant.
- **Finance-related actions:**
 - **Finance view:** It shows the stakeholder's financial status.
 - **Transfer money:** To give money to another stakeholder
 - **Request subsidy:** To ask for money to another stakeholder
- **Land transactions:** There are two action within this group: buy and sell land. The cost is defined by the involved stakeholders in the transaction. The transaction includes the buildings on the bought or sold land.
- **Inbox:** To send and receive messages among stakeholders.
- **Information on ECS:** This is not an action, properly said, since the players don't interact with the 3d-world or with other stakeholders. Specifically, it opens a panel where players can find information about ECS and their attributes (like table 2 but web-based and with search filters).

In this version, the stakeholders available to the players were decided in a workshop with urban scientists and urban planners. Eight roles were decided to be included in the Edible City Game:

- **Municipality:** the municipality is represented by the city hall and is the main responsible of the city development. They do not have the ability to construct ECSs but they can construct city parks (that can improve some indicators but compete for the space with ECS) and social housing. They have a good budget and are the responsible for the building permits.
- **Neighbours organization:** It represents the organized city neighbours. They are concerned about the liveability of the city. They can create communitarian ECSs but their budget is limited. It is the owner of all houses in behalf of the neighbours.
- **SME organization:** A organization representing the SMEs of the city devoted to urban agriculture. Their actions are aimed to create jobs in the city and making profit. They can create professional ECSs.
- **Consumers' cooperative:** A group of organized people with the aim to get local healthy food. They are interested in food sovereignty and in upscaling urban farming to the whole city. They can create professional ECSs.
- **Social third sector:** It represents the economic sector devoted to social issues, such as social workers or businesses that provide employ to vulnerable people. They are worried about social aspects such as fair employment, social cohesion and gentrification. They can create professional ECSs and social housing but their budget is limited.
- **Conservationist NGO:** A group of people worried about the city sustainability. They are aimed to improve all aspects of climate change mitigation and adaptation in the city. They can create communitarian ECSs but their budget is limited.
- **Educational sector:** A stakeholder representing teachers and families. Their interests lie on educational activities for students and in urban green areas for recreational purposes. They can create communitarian ECSs in the schools' gardens and outside (in the 2nd level).

- **Tourism promotion:** It represents the tourism sector, concerned about the capacity of the city to attract tourism. They do not have the ability to construct ECSs but they can construct city parks (in the 2nd level) and they have a good budget.
- **Inhabitants:** It is a not playable stakeholder, i.e. is not assigned to any player. The facilitator of the session can send messages to specific players in behalf of inhabitants to, for instance, protest an action done by any player.

The number of active characters depends on the number of players. The facilitator can choose which characters are activated or let the players choose which ones are left over.

Regarding the actions, they are designed to promote relationships among players. The main reason is that some stakeholders have the money while others have the ability to construct. Moreover, some players have assigned indicators that they cannot improve with their actions. Therefore, they will be forced to negotiate if they want to achieve their assignments. The available actions in each level for each character are described below.

The ownership of land is another important issue to for the playability, stakeholders must own the land where they want to construct or demolish. Moreover, selling land is a way to get money. As mentioned above, the neighbours' ass. are the owners of all private buildings. However, some stakeholders also have some properties at the beginning of the game:

- **Municipality:** It is the owner of public buildings such as municipal offices, public theatre and public spaces such as parks, squares and streets.
- **Educational sector:** It is the owner of all city schools.
- **SME organization:** It is the owner of all warehouses, offices and industries in the city.

Regarding neighbourhoods, by default, all of them are playable in this version. However, it can be decided before each session.

Besides the online rules, the players can interact each other face to face. Although this can happen at any moment while the game is running, any player can pause the game (asking to the facilitator) and force a negotiation or look for consensus.

2.7.4 Levels

Some modalities of the Edible City Game are divided in three levels. During each level, each character has a specific assignment, built on the assignment of the preceding level. The first level is the simplest, and each stakeholder will be able to focus on their primary task. In the last level, all responsibilities for all stakeholders require attention, with much overlap between different stakeholders. The decision of switch from one level to the next is facilitator's, in line with her perceptions regarding the session and the players' abilities.

In the modalities where the levels are not activated, there is only one character with all actions available. Likewise, all indicators are part of this character's assignment.

Level 1: Getting familiar

The aim of this first level is to get used with the platform's environment. How to navigate the 3D-world, how to perform an action, how to use the overlays to get additional information and what are the indicators.

Consequently, only a limited set of actions are available to each character and the assignment is compound by only one or two indicators, plus the budget indicator.

The storylines for each character are as follows:

- **Municipality:** Nowadays, public health in the city is under risk. Heatwaves are striking citizens every summer, and this is going worse from time to time. Therefore, your mission is to reduce the urban heat island effect of your city by building city parks or helping others to create edible city solutions. But you must be careful about green gentrification, social housing close to green areas is a strategy to prevent it.
- **Neighbours:** You are aware that some neighbours have been historically marginalized when the city has been greened. So, your main concern is to ensure that all neighbourhoods have the same amount of green per capita. However, you are also aware of the health benefits of people being involved in urban agriculture. Therefore, your mission is to build communitarian edible city solutions in those neighbourhoods with less green areas.
- **SME organization:** You believe that urban agriculture is an incredible solution to provide green jobs in a city and you want to prove it. Your mission in this first level is to construct professional edible city solutions to increase the number of people working in ECS.
- **Consumers' cooperative:** Getting fresh food in the city is more expensive from time to time. Moreover, most of that food is coming from far away, and you know that it is not sustainable. You are convinced that your city can produce an important part of the fresh food that is consumed. Your mission in this first level is to build edible city solutions to increase the food sovereignty of the city.
- **Social third sector:** The urban agriculture is an amazing place to work for people with social problems or with some disabilities. It allows to work in a team and outdoors, so improving the social relations and the wellbeing of workers. Therefore, you are interested in professional edible city solutions that provide jobs to vulnerable people. Contribute to build them. At the same time, you are worried about gentrification due to urban greening, increasing social housing close to green areas is a good strategy to prevent it.
- **Conservationist NGO:** The ecological footprint of the city must be reduced. Food sovereignty is a good strategy to reduce carbon emissions provoked by food importations. At the same time, the air in the city is becoming unbreathable. Something must be needed to reduce emissions or increase absorption. You know that urban agriculture can absorb air pollutants like other vegetation in the city, in addition, local food is able to reduce some of the traffic flows into the city.
- **Educational sector:** Working in a garden is a pleasant and insightful activity for kids and teenagers, they learn where the food comes from while they do some physical activity outdoors and commit to take care of a living being. In this first level, your mission is to provide as many schools as possible with edible gardens to involve kids and parents in growing their own food.
- **Tourism promotion:** As the city is struggling with social and environmental challenges, it becomes less attractive for tourist. However, you know that sustainable tourism is a good tool to help the city to become more resilient. Your mission in this first level is to help the other stakeholders to make a greener city, because tourists like city parks and green.

Level 2: Land scarcity

Once players are familiarized with the game, the second level is activated. In this level the set of actions and the assignments become more complex for each character. The interaction among players must also be increased if they want to achieve their assignments.

The storylines for each character at level 2 are:

Municipality: More public risks are arising. Not only about heatwaves but also regarding floods due to cloudbursts and air pollution. You need to continue with your task on reducing the heatwaves and preventing gentrification, but you also need to increase the water storage capacity of the city and find mechanisms to clean the air. Apart from adapting to climate change, your city is committed to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions in accordance with European Union policies. Therefore, you should start the transition to renewable energies by installing solar panels in public roofs.

- **Neighbours:** Besides access to green areas and participating in urban agriculture, heatwaves and air pollution are also affecting the neighbours' wellbeing. You know that the edible city solutions are working well but there are less and less available land in the city. Hence, you should start to think in alternatives like rooftop gardens.
- **SME organization:** Your volume of business is increasing properly, and more and more people is working in urban agriculture. However, your plots are threatened by cloudburst floods and you are interested in increasing the water storage capacity of the city to prevent these floods. To increase your business, it's time to start with innovative elements like rooftop and vertical gardens. In addition, you can use the same rooftops to invest in renewable energies, this way you can showcase the social responsibility of your companies.
- **Consumers' cooperative:** The food sovereignty is a good thing. But you want to move forward and make bigger your movement. Besides food sovereignty, you also want to increase the number of citizens working in urban agriculture and you want that all neighbourhoods have access to green areas thanks to edible city solutions to showcase the co-benefits of urban agriculture. But land is less and less available in the city. Hence, you should start to think in alternatives like rooftop gardens.
- **Social third sector:** You realized that edible city solutions are an amazing tool for social cohesion if gentrification is prevented. However, most of vulnerable people have difficulties to get affordable fresh food and their neighbourhoods suffer a chronic lack of green, which is affecting their wellbeing. Edible city solutions can also help to improve these issues. But land is less and less available in the city. Hence, you should start to think in alternatives like rooftop gardens.
- **Conservationist NGO:** Edible city solutions are improving the air quality and shortening the food chain, but it's not enough. More green areas and a circular food system are necessary to make the city more sustainable. At the same time, this is not a single hero fight, environmental education is needed to involve more people and communitarian gardens offers an amazing tool. But land is less and less available in the city. Hence, you should start to think in alternatives like rooftop gardens.
- **Educational sector:** Students and families are reacting so well to agriculture initiatives. The educational community has never been so united. You are decided to expand the edible gardens beyond the limits of the school and start initiatives in the neighbourhoods with the aim to bring the urban green and fresh food closer to families, especially in the most vulnerable neighbourhoods.
- **Tourism promotion:** Tourists are more and more exigent with their requirements. You need to improve their visit satisfaction. You must find mechanisms to reduce the heat in the city and to improve the air quality. In addition, floods are not a good marketing strategy for the city, you should find mechanisms to increase the water storage capacity of the city to prevent floods after a cloudburst.

Level 3: Let's work together

In this level, the players must leave back their characters' interest and play together for the common wellbeing. All characters' assignments are covering all indicators equally weighted, thus all players have the same goals in this level and they can cooperate each other without limitations. Besides, a new interesting action is activated for municipality and SME: the capacity for demolishing buildings.

The storyline is the same for all characters:

You made significant improvements to the city but it's not enough. It's time to leave back your personal interests and work together for the general interest of all citizens. To facilitate this huge task, some of you can demolish buildings to create open areas in the city, but be cautious because great power carries big responsibility. And remember, it's time to cooperate among all of you.

Table 3. Indicators activated at each level for each character.

	Municipality	Neighbours	SME	Consumers	Social	Conservationist	Education	Tourism
Climate adaptation	1	2	3	3	3	3	3	2
Water management	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	2
Green accessibility	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	1
Air quality	2	2	2	3	3	1	3	2
Public participation	3	1	3	3	3	2	1	3
Green justice	3	1	3	2	2	3	2	3
Green economy	3	3	1	2	1	3	3	3
Food sovereignty	3	3	3	1	2	1	2	3
Social housing	1				1			
Solar panels	2		2					
Budget	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 4. Actions available to each character at each level

	Municipality	Neighbours	SME	Consumers	Social	Conservationist	Education	Tourism
Construct communitarian ECS		1				1	2	
Construct professional ECS			1	1	1			
Construct rooftop communitarian ECS		2				2	2	
Construct rooftop professional ECS			2	2	2			
Construct communitarian ECS in the school garden							1	
Construct rooftop communitarian ECS in the school							1	
Convert streets to edible streets	2							
Upgrade trees with fruit trees	3							

Construct city park	1							1
Construct social housing	1				1			
Install solar panels	2		2					
Demolish	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Revert	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Transfer Money	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Request subsidy		2	3	3	3	2	2	
Buy land	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
Sell land	2	3	2	2	2	3	3	1
Inbox	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Construct on open land refers to construct new buildings on empty plots, the player must own the land to construct. When the building is constructed on urban land it is an upgrade, paved areas, green areas and parking lots can be upgraded to ECS or to city park. Players must own the land to upgrade to city park and to professional ECS but they do not to upgrade to communitarian ECS.

At the beginning of the game, a specific budget is provided to each character. However, the facilitator can send additional money to any player whenever it is necessary (Table 5). For instance, the neighbours' budget is enough to build an allotment of 200 m². The budgets of municipality and tourism promotion are bigger because they are supposed to be the subsidizers of the rest of the characters.

Table 5. Budgets (€) of each player

Municipality	2.000.000
Neighbours	100.000
SME	300.000
Consumers	100.000
Social	200.000
Conservationist	50.000
Education	50.000
Tourism	3.000.000

2.8 Edible City Game's modalities

After the tests of versions from 1.0 to 2.0, one conclusion was that the game mechanics are hard to learn, especially in a first session. This issue hampered the learning experience because players had to focus on handle the game interface or, sometimes, they get frustrated. Therefore, in this version, different game modalities are proposed to adjust the game to the players skills and expectations. The modality of the game can be decided by the facilitator or by the responsible of the City Team a few hours before.

At the end of this section, a comparison among modalities are shown in a table to facilitates to decision-making process of choosing a modality.

2.8.1 Full expert

It is the conventional modality. Is a multiplayer session where each player has its own computer. Players interact among them through the game session by sending messages, doing requests,

buying and selling land. Each player has a character assigned in the game with different available actions and different goals to achieve to simulate the planning process and foster virtual interaction among players. The levels are also activated

2.8.2 Guided full expert

It is the same logics than full expert but game interface of all characters is handled by the facilitator and projected to a shared screen to avoid the complexities of interacting with the game interface. The game is played in rounds with the following sequence:

1. Facilitator switches to the character's view.
2. Players takes a decision on pending requests from other players
3. Player decides an action to do (buy land, construct, upgrade, demolish...)
4. Facilitator executes the action on the game.

2.8.3 Simulation contest

In this modality, the characters are deactivated (there is only one character with full capabilities), and neither are levels. The players are split in different teams that compete to plan the best possible city. The session of each team is independent from the others, thus the teams do not interact among them during the game. Each team has a facilitator that handles the game interface on behalf of the team. At the end of the game, the solutions of each team are compared to know which team has achieve the better outcomes based on city indicators.

2.8.4 Direct democracy (with imposed assignments)

This modality is played in one session projected on a shared screen. Thus, the virtual characters and the levels are deactivated. Cards with a character and an assignment based on two indicators are delivered among players who must keep it secret. The game is played in rounds with this sequence:

1. Players decide an action to do (construct, upgrade, demolish...)
2. The action is submitted to the vote of all players.
3. If the action is approved by simple majority, the facilitator executes the action on the game interface.

At the end of the game, the players share their secret roles and assignments and the session is discussed.

2.8.5 Direct democracy (with free assignments)

This modality is a variant of previous one. In this case, the cards with assignments are not delivered. Instead, players choose two indicators that will be their assignment. Likewise, they must keep it secret until the end of the game.

2.8.6 Single player

This modality is supposed to be useful for municipality practitioners that want to analyse different scenarios or different solutions. It can be played using a character or using full capabilities. It will depend on the interests of the player. It is the unique modality that can be player full online.

2.8.7 Modalities comparison

Table 6. Modalities comparison

	Full expert	Guided full expert	Simulation contest	Direct democracy (imposed)	Direct democracy (free)	Single-player
Aims (1-3)	1,25	2,25	2,75	2,75	2,75	2
To showcase the main urban challenges and how they can be measured	Medium	Medium	Good	Good	Good	Good
To understand how different ECSs address these urban challenges.	Poor	Medium	Good	Good	Good	Good
To empathize with other stakeholders in the city and their conflicting interests.	Poor	Good	Medium	Good	Good	Poor
To reach consensus about strategies to implement ECSs with the City Team	Poor	Medium	Good	Medium	Medium	Poor
Number of players	4-8	4-8	4-16	4-8	4-8	1
Players' skills requirements	Hard	Easy	Easy	Easy	Easy	Hard
Game functionalities	5	5	1	1	1	5
Characters	Activated	Activated	Deactivated	Offline (not in the game mechanics)	Offline (not in the game mechanics)	Optional
Levels	Activated	Activated	Deactivated	Deactivated	Deactivated	Optional
Land property	Activated	Activated	Deactivated	Deactivated	Deactivated	Optional
Budget	Activated	Activated	Activated	Deactivated	Deactivated	Optional
Assignments	Activated	Activated	Deactivated	Offline (not in the game mechanics)	Offline (not in the game mechanics)	Optional
Infrastructure requirements	Hard	Easy	Hard	Easy	Easy	Easy
Computers	5-9	1	2-4	1	1	1
Facilitators	1	1	2-4	1	1	0
Projector	1	1	1	1	1	0
Big screens	0	0	2-4	0	0	0

2.9 Data requirements

The objects and the indicators described above are based on the real world. Therefore, they must be fed with actual data. This section details all the required data and their purposes:

Table 7. Data requirements to build the Edible City Game.

Data	Description	Scale	Format	Source
Heat effect of ECSs	The new functions representing ECSs must have a heat effect value to calculate their influence on the heat stress indicator	Function	Numeric (°C)	UNESCO-IHE EdiCitNet simple models
Water storage capacity of ECSs	The new functions representing ECSs must	Function	Numeric (m ³ /m ²)	EdiCitNet survey

	have a water storage value to calculate their influence on the water storage indicator			EdiCitNet simple models
NO₂ absorption	The capacity of absorbing NO ₂ must be defined for all nature-based functions, including the ECSs.	Function	Numeric (µg/m ²)	EdiCitNet simple models
People involved in ECSs	People involved must be estimated for each ECS function.	Function	Numeric (person/m ²)	EdiCitNet survey
Income level	The income level is necessary to calculate the fair access to green areas.	Neighbourhood or finer.	Numeric (€/year)	Municipality
Jobs in ECSs	Created jobs must be estimated for each ECS function.	Function	Numeric (full time person/m ²)	EdiCitNet survey
Workforce	The workforce is necessary to calculate the impact of jobs created by ECSs	Neighbourhood or finer.	Numeric (person)	Municipality
Food production	The new functions representing ECSs must have a food production value to calculate their influence on the food sovereignty.	Function	Numeric (kg/m ² /year)	EdiCitNet survey EdiCitNet simple models
Buildings in the city	The buildings are required to build the 3D world. They should include the number of floors, the building function and whether they have a rooftop.	City	GIS data (polygons)	Open street maps Land cadastre Municipality
Streets	The buildings are required to build the 3D world	City	GIS data (polygons)	Open street maps
Traffic intensity	The traffic intensity of each street is necessary to calculate the emissions of NO ₂	Street	Numeric (cars/day)	Municipality
Public areas	Including squares, parks and others	City	GIS data (polygons)	Municipality
Trees	A dataset of urban forestry is important for the heat stress indicator, but also for improving the aesthetics of the 3D world	City	GIS data (points)	Municipality Land cadastre
Land covers	Land covers are an essential part of terrain and they play several roles in the indicators	City	GIS data (raster)	ESRI
Elevations digital model (EDM)	EDM is an essential part of terrain.	City	GIS data (raster)	ESRI
Zoning plan	The zoning plan plays an important role on the permits for constructing	City	GIS data (polygons)	Municipality
Construction costs	The new functions representing ECSs must have a construction cost value to calculate their	Function	Numeric (€/m ²)	EdiCitNet survey

	impact on the budget when they are constructed			
Educational centres	A GIS layer with all schools in the city.	City	GIS data (points)	Municipality
Edible city solutions	The ECS already existing in the city are important to build a rigorous base scenario	City	GIS data (polygons)	EdiCitNet survey

2.10 Data feedback to users

In this section, the feedback from the game to the players is defined. Which scores, rewards and trophies feedback the player’s actions?

In the Edible City Game, each player visualizes a progress bar in their screen (Figure 7). The progress bar scores according to the weighting of the indicators. That is, the progress bar is the weighted sum of all indicators’ scores, in other words, the assignment. Therefore, reaching a score of 100% in the progress bar is the main goal of the player which is achieved by scoring 100% in all indicators that are assigned to that character.

Players can also find information on the individual indicators (actual, target and “to do” measures). Moreover, overlays change according to actions made during the game, so players can visualize how the city is progressing. All this information can be seen in the players

Simultaneously, every time that a player develops an action with a repercussion on the indicators, a panel shows to what extent this action is modifying the indicators.

Figure 12. Example of information panel about the impact of an action (demolish in this case) has on the indicators’ scores.

2.11 Game evaluation layer

The game evaluation layer has the aim to provide a visualization of the players' learning and their evolution within the game. In the Edible City Game this is the log session. The facilitator can download at any moment a log session with all the actions that the players have done in this session. This information provides an evaluation on the progress within a session but also a comparison among different sessions to evaluate the progress through the participation process or between different approaches such as promoting more consensus or prohibiting the offline negotiations, for instance.

2.12 Users' feedback on the game

At the end of a session, the users will share their experience and their conclusions about the game and the ECS.

In addition, they will be asked to fill a survey to evaluate the aesthetics of the game and the serious content (Constantinescu et al., 2017). The survey will have the following questions:

1. Which stakeholder you played with?
 - Municipality
 - Neighbours organization
 - SME organization
 - Consumers' cooperative
 - Social third sector
 - Conservationist NGO
 - Educational sector
 - Tourism promotion
2. To what extent do you agree with the following sentences (Likert scale from 1 to 7):
 - I make the most of my time playing with the Edible City Game.
 - I improved my knowledge about the role of ECSs in the urban challenges.
 - I better understood the interests of other stakeholders in the city planning.
 - I consider myself very aware of sustainability concerns.
 - The game instructions were very clear.
 - The game was really playful
 - The interaction with the other players was stimulating
 - My actions during the game depended on the other players' actions
 - I influenced the other players' actions
 - The players pursued a common goal.
 - I felt comfortable playing the game.
3. To what extent the game fulfilled your expectations (Likert scale from 1 to 7).
4. The duration of the game was (1 too long – 7 too short)
5. Are you used to videogames? (1 nothing – 7 expert)
6. Do you have experience in (1 nothing – 7 expert):
 - Urban planning
 - Urban agriculture
 - Nature-based solutions
7. You are
 - Male
 - Female
 - Others
8. How old are you?

9. What is the highest educational degree you obtained?

- I do not have studies
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education

10. In which city neighbour do you live?

The answers of the survey, together with the log sessions and direct observation during the sessions, will feed the iterative process in which new improved versions of the game should arise.

3 Infrastructure requirements for game sessions

The infrastructure required differs on each modality (Table 6). However, Tygron products utilize gaming technology as their driving force, most notably the 3D visualization. This technology requires that the computer must meet certain requirements to be able to run Tygron products. These requirements specifically refer to processor (CPU), memory (RAM) and videocard (GPU).

- Screen resolution of at least 1280x800 pixels
- Windows 8 or higher (64 bits).
- Optimal minimum processor like AMD Athlon Core 2 Premium,
- RAM: 8 GB
- Videocard which scores above 1000 in the Benchmark score.

More information can be found on Tygron's wiki⁵.

4 What is new in this version?

The version 2.0 was tested on October 9, 2020 with researchers from ICRA, UdG and practitioners from Girona's municipality. From the feedback of that session, some bugs were fixed and some minor improvements were made in version 2.1. However, the major innovation in this version are the game modalities.

Improvement	Target
Budget weight modified to not interfere with the progress bar	Indicators
ECS are coloured with a more intense green	Functions
Game modalities are established	Storyline
Information about upgrade combination included in the information panel	Actions
Schools are named	Geodata
Streets are upgradable to edible streets (communitarian gardens)	Actions
Upgrades on the ground are replaced by the sequence of demolish and construct	Actions

Below is the information about previous versions:

Version	Released	Session date	Session location	Comments
1.0	03/09/2020	04/09/2020	ICRA	Initial beta version
1.1	15/09/2020	--	--	Some bugs fixed and minor improvements were added.
2.0	09/10/2020	09/10/2020	ICRA	Major changes in storyline

⁵ <https://support.tygron.com/wiki/Requirements>

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